

THEORY OF CONCEPT IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS

Saydakhmatova Hilola Ibromkhim qizi

The department of Integrated English language course №2
Uzbekistan State World Languages University

Abstract: *This article outlines the theory and description of concept in cognitive linguistics. The concept can of various type and different complexity, it has a probabilistic structure, its boundaries are indefinite and mobile. It is a phenomenon of the same order as concept and understanding*

Keywords: *Concept, understanding, cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, conceptual core.*

The term "concept" was used during the "linguistic renaissance" from the beginning of the 90s of the 20th century, primarily by ¹D.S. Likhachev and Yu.S. Stepanov, who revised it and gave it a detailed interpretation. The active use of this term in cognitive linguistics, the paradigm of linguistic conceptualism, and linguoculturalism is explained by the need to include the missing cognitive "link" in their categorical apparatus, the content of which, in addition to the concept, includes the associative. As a mental formation of a higher level of abstraction, the concept is mainly related to the word. It follows that it contains all the information of communicative importance, except for relevance to the topic. First of all, it shows the position of the sign in the lexical system of the language: its paradigmatic, syntagmatic and derivative connections - what F. Saussure called ²"significance" and ultimately "reflecting the linguistic value of a language. extralinguistic object'. The semantic content of the concept also includes all the pragmatic information of the linguistic sign related to its expressive and representative functions, which are fully compatible with "experience" and "intensity".

¹ Лихачев Д.С. Логический анализ языка. Культурные концепты. М., 1991.С.280-287

² Красавский Н.А. Эмоциональные концепты в немецкой и русской лингвокультурах. Монография. Волгоград, 2001.С.40-59

In Uzbek linguistics, the notion of "concept" has different interpretations. For example, Sh. S. Safarov emphasizes that "the perception of the material world is the birth of the concept of the perceived object - events, and later this concept is formed as a mental model - concept and receives a material name."

O. Q. Yusupov defines the concept as "a complex of knowledge in our minds about something or an event in the external or internal world, images about it and positive, negative, neutral attitudes towards it, i.e. evaluations."³

It is known that in recent years, the term "concept" has been widely used. At the same time, the terms "concept", "meaning" are used together with the term "concept". Many scientists claim that concept, understanding and meaning are phenomena of the same order.

It is a phenomenon of the same order as concept and understanding. Concept comes from the Latin word "conceptus" - "understanding", from the verb "concupere" - "to understand, to imagine", that is, when translated literally, it means "understanding, concept". In scientific language, these two words act as synonyms for each other, but they are used only occasionally, and now they are very clearly demarcated.

Concept and understanding are terms of different disciplines; the second one is mainly used in logic and philosophy, and the first concept is a term in a branch of logic - mathematical logic, which has recently taken root in cultural studies and is considered the main one in the science of culture.

The terms "concept" and "notion" are the most important special lexical units of modern science. Clarification of their content and structure makes it possible to distinguish their use and helps to establish terminological clarity in the categorical apparatus of separate disciplines, because it is known that one of the conditions for the successful operation of the term is clarity.

The concept of lexical units and the problem of interdependence of the meaning volume V.A. Maslova, Yu.S. Stepanov, I.A. Sternin, M.V. attracted the

³ Юсупов Ў.Қ- Маъно, тушунча, концепт ва тилшуносковокултурема атамалари хусусида // Стилистика тилшуносликнинг замонавий йўналишларида: Иккинчи амалий конференция материаллари. – Тошкент, 2011. – Б. 49

attention of such scientists. Information on this problem can be found in the works of S. G. Vorkachev, V. Z. Demyankov, L. V. Popova, M. A. Levina, V. G. Kuznetsov, E. A. Sorokina. Many researchers believe that the terms differ in modern meaning and usage.

V.N. Telia was one of the first to use the term "concept" in the analysis of phraseological units and noted that the term "concept" can be replaced by the term "concept". A concept is always structured knowledge. It reflects not only the essential properties of the object, but also everything filled with knowledge about its essence in a given language community.

According to V. G. Kuznetsov, a number of scientists use the terms "concept" and "concept" as synonyms.⁴

Yu.S. Stepanov stated that "concept" and "notion" are phenomena of the same order, which correspond to each other according to their internal form. Many researchers believe that concept and understanding are related to each other as a genus and species⁵.

M.A. Levina emphasizes that the concept is a type term (hyponym) in relation to more complex formations that make up general concepts (hyperonyms). According to M. V. Pimenova and O. N. Kondratieva, the concept is "one of the structural elements of the concept" or "one of the variants of existence, an embodiment of the concept".

As noted by I. A. Sternin and Z. D. Popova, the concept is an "umbrella term" that includes many mental phenomena. Concept, according to them, "is a concept that reflects the most general, important features of an object or phenomenon, the result of their rational reflection and understanding". In the process of evolution, the concept loses its secondary, random, individual characteristics. According to S. G. Vorkachev, the structure of the concept is complex, it includes the image and the concept in abbreviated form: "linguistic concept is characterized by heterogeneity

⁴ Кузнецов В. Г. Корреляция: специальный концепт – понятие – значение – термин // Вопросы когнитивной лингвистики. 2012. № 2. С. 24–33.

⁵ Концепт // Степанов Ю. С. Константы: словарь русской культуры: 3-е изд. М.: Академический проект, 2004. С. 42.

and multiple attributes, removing discursiveness from the concept. The expression of meaning, from the image - the metaphorical and emotive nature of the image, and from the meaning - the introduction of its name into the lexical system of the language". In addition, S. G. Vorkachev distinguishes between the "broad" and "narrow" understanding of the concept. In a narrow sense, he equates the concept with the concepts of everyday life .

V. A. Maslova believed that "there is no impassable border between concept and concept: under certain conditions, concepts can become concepts." However, due to the widespread use of the lexeme "concept" in the scientific discourse, it became necessary to differentiate the use of the lexemes concept and concept.

According to V. Z. Demyankov, according to the internal form, the words "concept" and "concept" are synonymous: "Concepts and notions, which are always present in scientific discourse, are historical doublets. However, modern (scientific and non-scientific) in use, these terms are distinguished by their usage." The term concept can be used in everyday speech, it is known to all representatives of language culture, and concept is a term that is understandable to specialists in a narrow scientific field: "Concept" refers to the field of science, in particular, philosophy; "concept" is common property. According to Yu.S. Stepanov, both the lexeme "concept" and the lexeme "concept" can be used in modern scientific discourse, but they have different functional loads: "Concept and notion are terms of different disciplines; the concept is mainly used in logic and philosophy, and the concept is a term in a branch of logic - mathematical logic, and has recently been strengthened in cultural science and cultural studies. As noted by E. A. Sorokina, the lexeme "concept" is used in automotive engineering, cognitive science, history of art, general linguistics and its departments such as linguoculturology, cognitive linguistics, in addition to the listed fields of knowledge. Comparing the nature of the terms under consideration, it can be noted that, according to André Comte-Sponville, the compiler of the "Philosophical Dictionary", the concept is recognized by the mind without any action, having a clearly defined internal form. "Understanding is the result of mental

effort; concept is the condition of this effort. A concept can serve as a tool, but it must first be created.

A concept is a starting point for more material or reflection. The above definition is based on the fact that the concept is the basic unit of thinking, which is the source of complex mental actions, because the mind primarily works with concepts as minimal units of mental activity that are the basis for judgments and conclusions; the concept is a complex, hierarchical concept, often with several layers.

According to V.G. Kuznetsov, concept and notion are connected as "logical" and "mental". He focuses on the function of the concept as the formation of logical thinking and emphasizes the role of the concept in storing information about a part of the world. At the same time, M.A. Levina believes that concepts are artificial formations, and the concept is taken as a given for all representatives of a certain group of people. Indeed, Z. D. Popova and I. A. Sternin point out that concepts are often created by linguists who define them in dictionaries⁶.

The concept has a mental essence and is closely related to emotional, subjective components. According to Yu.S. Stepanov, the concept is experienced before it enters the consciousness, it is closely related to the emotions caused by the stimulus object. L. V. Popova also emphasizes it as follows: "The linguistic and cultural direction refers to the concept of the intellectual and mental activity of a person, and the concept includes feelings, emotions, images, symbols."

Many scientists believe that, in contrast to the concept, which tends to be inclusive and specific in the formation of the concept, it has cultural characteristics (see the works of S. G. Vorkachev, V. A. Maslova, V. V. Oshchepkova, Yu. S. Stepanov). Thus, S. G. Vorkachev is convinced that the "concept" in the linguistic and cultural texts is a literal cultural meaning, and it is "usually" a linguistic and cultural concept (linguoconcept)⁷.

⁶ Попова З. Д., Стернин И. А. Семантико-когнитивный анализ языка. Воронеж: Истоки, 2007. 250 с.

⁷ Воркачев С. Г. Постулаты лингвоконцептологии // Антология концептов / под ред. В. И. Карасика, И. А. Стернина. Т. 1. Волгоград: Парадигма, 2005. С. 10–13

Thus, M. V. Pimenova believes that "a concept is a national image (idea, symbol) complicated by individual representative signs." V.V. Oshchepkova describes specific, culturally determined words that differ in the level of brightness of the presence of a certain feature in different cultures. Analyzing the internal structure of the terms in question, it can be noted that the concept is a complex multi-layered formation that covers "the entire body of knowledge about an object or event: changes in the history of their emergence." ". Thus, Yu.S. Stepanov confirms that the concept includes both conceptual features and "everything that makes it a fact of culture."

According to V. G. Kuznetsov, "a concept as a mental image of a fragment of reality has a complex, hierarchically organized structure that includes all types of knowledge."

The concept can be divided into scope and content. Volume refers to the entire class of objects that meet this definition, and content is the sum of the most important features of the concept. The concept has content and structure. The content of the concept is structured by cognitive features and has a core, near and far periphery. The structure of the concept includes such components as an interpretation field, a symbol, an image, an image. In philosophy, a concept captures the essence of the thing or phenomenon under study: "Sometimes a concept is combined with the content of a general name, the meaning behind such a name." In linguistics, the concept is usually connected with the meaning, and the concept is connected with the content of the concept, with the meaning. For example, Yu. S. Stepanov analyzes the concept of "rooster" as an example in the "Dictionary of Russian Culture", the meaning of which is associated with certain types of characteristics of the bird, and additional meanings through representation and associations is formed.

As stated in the Encyclopedia of the Philosophy of Science, it is necessary to distinguish the meaning of the terms "concept" and "concept". He focuses on such features of the concept as objectivity, independence from communication, impersonality, direct connection with language structures. The concept is formed through speech and manifests itself in it, as a result of which it is "extremely

subjective" and directed at the listener: "Memory and imagination are integral properties of the concept, on the other hand, the concept synthesizes in itself the three faculties of the soul and directed to the past as an act of memory, to the future as an act of imagining, to the present as an act of judgment.

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